

Components and Restrictions in Phase Rule

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An alternative definition of the 'components' has been offered without mentioning the 'composition of each of the phases' and 'restrictions'. The number of components is equal to the number of chemical species except when (1) one or more of the chemical species break down to products in more than one phase and (2) the reactive chemical species are taken in a stoichiometric ratio.

Beginners in phase rule study find difficulty in making a distinction between components and the chemical species of a system. One may not be able to appreciate the restriction (minimum number of the chemical species with the help of which one can express the composition of each phase) imposed on the definition of the components. The three obvious reasons for this are that (1) most of the systems have the same number of components as the number of chemical species, (2) one sometimes confuses between the compositions of each phase separately and of the system as a whole, and (3) great injustice has been done to this term 'component' by classifying the phase rule study on the basis of the number of components and we hardly ever use the definition to ascertain the number of components. We must not overlook, however, the great simplification that is done by such a classification and that there is nothing wrong with it if the importance of components is lost sight of. It is the restriction that overburdens this generalisation of the Phase rule.

The difficulty about the number of components and restrictions has been mentioned by Richards¹, Bowden², and many others³⁻⁶. Bowden postulated a modified phase rule to solve this difficulty :

$$P + F + R = C + 2 - r \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

(where C is regarded as the number of chemical species rather than the number of components; P and F have the usual significance and R and r are the number of chemical equations and the number of restrictions imposed on the system respectively). The introduction of r in the above equation is empirical and more often its exact nature is not understood. One has to make use of this term under certain conditions during a phase rule study when the degree of freedom is less than that given by the equation;

$$P + F + R = C + 2 \quad \dots \quad (b)$$

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 983.

2. *Nature*, 1938, 141, 331.

3. Jongeb, *J. So. Polytch.*, 1931, No. 30, 181; *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, 16, 1690.

4. Brinkley, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1946, 14, 563.

5. Prigogine and Desay, *Ibid.*, 1947, 15, 614.

6. Peneloux, *Compt. rend.*, 1949, 228, 1737.

According to the definition, the components are connected with the composition of each of the phases and hence let us see what are the conditions under which there are too many chemical species to afford the composition of each of the phases or under which the starting chemical species are insufficient to define the composition of all the phases. Calcium carbonate on heating dissociates to two phases and here is a case where the composition of CaO or CO_2 phases would not be given by CaCO_3 alone. Also all the chemical species taken together are more than the necessary number. On the other hand, NH_4Cl dissociates to ammonia and hydrogen chloride in the same phase and the composition of the vapour phase can be expressed by NH_4Cl . It is a one-component system and not three or two as might be expected. Hence it appears that the breaking down of a chemical species into products in at least two phases is connected with the number of components being different from the number of chemical species.

A similar situation exists about the term 'restriction'. There is no doubt that each restriction reduces the number of components by one, but how? The important restrictions commonly met with are:

- (i) When two or more chemical species are taken in a stoichiometric ratio.
- (ii) When the compositions of the two or more phases become identical. The phases may either merge or remain separate.

A little thought about these restrictions would make it clear that these refer to a situation when two or more chemical species may form a chemical compound. In certain cases compound may not be formed, but the behaviour of the system corresponds to that of a compound.

One definition involving the limited number of chemical species and the restrictions could be:

The number of components in a system is normally equal to the number of chemical species except when (I) one or more of the chemical species break down to products in two or more different phases and (II) the reactive chemical species (in the same phase) are taken in a stoichiometric ratio.

In case (I) the number of components is more than, and in case (II), less than the number of chemical species. As a general rule, the difference in the number of components and the number of chemical species is equal to the increase in the number of phases as a result of chemical reaction.

The definition is more or less similar to that expressed by Bowden* in his modified Phase Rule, but it has the advantage of being a form of statement. It includes the number of reactions and the restrictions in one.

Ordinarily when we talk of the components, we mention them in connection with the system being a one-component or a two-component one and so on, and we want the components to be known from the number of chemical species we start with for the phase rule study. It is then the number of phases and the degrees of freedom that change under varying conditions and not the number of components. This fixed number must be known from the very start of the study. In ordinary course, when there is no chemical reaction, this number is equal to the number of chemical species we start with. If one or more chemical species break down into more than one phase, the number of components will be more than the number of chemical species.

The emphasis is on 'the products being in different phases'. If, however, the products are in the same phase, the first part of the statement will hold good even though there may be chemical reaction. In the dissociation of ammonium chloride the reaction takes place, but the products, ammonia and hydrogen chloride gases, are in the same phase and hence there is no increase in the number of phases as a result of chemical reaction. The only change is the conversion of solid phase into gaseous phase. The number of components is one because the number of species started with is also one. The situation can be regarded as solid ammonium chloride being in contact with its vapour and hence it is a one-component system. The generally expressed view in some of the books that the number of components is equal to the number of chemical species minus the number of chemical equations, is not always true or otherwise further limitation of the system has to be prescribed.

Calcium carbonate (one phase) on phase-chemical reaction provides two different phases, CaO and CO₂, and hence the number of components is 2, one more than the number of chemical species. If there were a chemical reaction expressed by the equation. (hypothetical):

the increase in the number of phases is two and hence the number of components will be 3.

A system of Na₂CO₃.10 H₂O undergoes the meriteotic reaction:

affording products in two different phases and hence the number of components would be two although the number of chemical species started with is one.

A system of KCl, NaCl, and H₂O is a three-component one because there are three chemical species and there is no chemical reaction. A system of KCl, NaNO₃, and water (three chemical species) is, however, capable of undergoing the chemical reaction:

If we take KCl or NaNO₃ or both in excess, it will be observed that the two solid phases, KCl and NaNO₃, cannot remain together in equilibrium with water and one of them will go into solution. There will be only two phases, solution and KCl or NaNO₃, whichever is in excess. If KCl is in excess, it can undergo one of the following reactions depending on the initial composition of the mixture.

In cases (1) and (3), it is breaking down of solution (i) in two different phases and in case (2), KCl and solution (i) react to form three different phases. In all the cases there is an increase in the number of phases by one and hence the number of components will be four, one more than the number of chemical species.

Similar conclusion would be arrived at if we replace KCl by NaNO₃ in the above phase-chemical reaction scheme. If we start with reciprocal salt pair, NaCl and KNO₃,

and water, the two solids can now remain in equilibrium with solution and can undergo one of the following reactions:

The overall reaction shows the breaking down of solution (iii) in two different phases. The number of components is therefore four.

In the case of a two-component system, Mg and Zn, if we take these in gram atom ratio of 1 : 2 (corresponding to the compound MgZn_2), the behaviour of the system is that of a one-component one though the chemical species are two. A similar situation exists in the case of azeotropic mixtures when these boil unchanged in composition like those of pure substances and hence these may be regarded as pseudo compounds and the system will be one-component one and not two.

The definition of components, defined in this communication, is true for reactive species, but it may be extended to nonreactive species also where the restriction has to be explained. In liquid systems, critical solution temperature and plait point refer to fixed compositions of the species. The situation may therefore be likened to compound formation and the number of components will be less than the number of chemical species.

It must, however, be explicitly mentioned that the definition propounded is not unique. It is essentially the same as embodied in the modified phase rule but with a different and probably a simpler approach. It is a definition without mentioning the terms 'composition of the phases' and 'restrictions'.